

Individual Reflective Critique Report

BM-5102 Organisational Behaviour

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BEFORE EXPERIENCE

About 14 weeks ago, I submitted a paper about my intention to pursue a Masters Degree in Management which until now still felt like a 360 degrees shift from my major during my Bachelor's Degree. In the paper, I also wrote about my decision to take BM-5102 Organisational Behaviour as one of the modules for this first semester. After a year break from academics, the first few months of Master was chaotic. With the current COVID-19 pandemic going on, the new norms and the needs for online learning, everything seems abnormal and a bit tormenting. Nevertheless, it was indeed a journey worth taking.

This module named Organisational Behaviour largely consists of a group case study and an individual analysis (IA) assignment, aside from discussions both online and offline. Firstly, I will be reflecting on the case study assignment that was done in a group. In late August, myself and two others decided to choose a topic titled "*Motivations of gerai stall entrepreneurs to become halalpreneurs*". The study aims to address the factors associated with a propensity for halal entrepreneurship among gerai stall entrepreneurs. We wanted to understand the drivers of gerai stall entrepreneurs to become halalpreneurs. Specifically, to identify whether the gerai stall entrepreneurs possess the characteristics of halalpreneurs and to investigate the motivational theories that fit in halal entrepreneurship. Finding team members was easy but choosing a topic for the case study was somewhat challenging. It took us quite some times to actually come to an agreement as a team. Reflecting back at that very moment, I realized how carefree I actually was. Even when and/or after I suggested my preferred topic(s), deep down, I did not really mind if our team will end up choosing a different topic. I was up to any challenge given to me but things were not always smooth-sailing, to say the least. The heart changes along the way.

In regards to the case study, the project goals were first, to interview as many gerai stall entrepreneurs at Gadong Night Market as we could. In the early evening of Friday, 25th October 2020, we decided to do some observations at the night market first. Using a non-probability method, specifically purposive sampling, we planned to recruit at least 20 potential study participants that day. We did direct observations on businesses (i.e. products they sell) and the people whether they are suitable for the study or not. This was believed to have allowed us to have a good and in-depth understanding of a phenomenon and situation as well as the behaviour of the participants in that setting. As Atieno (2009) asserts, studying the whole situation helps evaluate the complexity and ensure that conclusions take into account both unique and general factors.

Then, the samples were approached in order to get their contact details and their readiness to participate in the research. Little that I know, it was not that straightforward. My groupmates and I went from 1) merely taking the phone numbers of businesses from their banner, then 2) asking the numbers directly but acting as if we were customers, to eventually 3) going directly and telling the truths - that we are UBD students wanting to interview them. The first two methods were rather painless but in the midst of finding more participants, I realized the importance of actually being honest and how going with the first and second method would actually cause us more work and can be very time-consuming. In essence, we would have to contact the business owners again at a later time and ask their willingness to participate in the study. I shared my concerns with my groupmates and they acknowledged it. Hence, we decided to attempt method

number 3. Going with the third method was very complicated nevertheless. We encountered several business owners who refused to attend to us, knowing that we are students. One individual, a middle-aged man, in particular, gave us a hard time. Here, I realized that not all entrepreneurs are open to the idea of sharing knowledge. Based on my observation, senior citizens are keener to share their thoughts and expertise compared to their relatively younger counterparts, although not all. Reflecting back to that very moment, I now realized how essential the skills of approaching other people are and how crucial it is to make people understand our main intentions to avoid misconceptions. At the end of that observation day, we knew we had to change the game plan.

After some fruitful discussions with the lecturer, and sharing our concerns, we were suggested to be opened to the possibilities of conducting research at different stalls instead of just focusing only on the Gadong Night Market. Some of us had actually thought about it but did not think that changes were possible. Listening to that one suggestion from the lecturer felt like approval and it gave us hopes. Eventually, we ended up conducting interviews at three different places namely, the Tutong Market, Kianggeh Market, and Gadong Night Market where we got five, five and four participants respectively.

In regards to the individual analysis, on the other hand, I always knew from the start that I wanted to do research on women leaders, as this feels the closest to the heart. I also wanted to study what impact(s) women can give to organisations today be it in the public and in the private sector. The project initially aimed at interviewing as many as 20 women leaders of Brunei Darussalam across different disciplines and backgrounds, which includes presidents, CEO, managers, vice-chancellors and etc. However, it was evident from the rejected ethics form application that this study was too ambitious, broad, and needs to be narrowed down. Hence, again after some discussions with the lecturer and sharing my thoughts and concerns, my then approved research title was *“Women Who Lead: Success and Challenges of Ten Education Leaders in Brunei Darussalam”*.

The study aims to analyse in-depth how women manage the gendered norms of leadership in organisations as well as to uncover the reasons behind women leaders’ success and challenges, particularly their way of handling difficult situations that they encountered in their professional and personal life. Women leaders in the education sector include leaders that are in higher institutions, schools and learning centres. By understanding the way of management and learning the success and challenges of women leaderships, it was hoped that people can see the importance of gender equality as a fundamental human right and an essential foundation for an effective and successful organisation, also for a peaceful, prosperous and sustainable world in general. It was also hoped that valuable lessons and advice can be learned from the success stories of these women for the benefit of myself and other current or aspiring leaders.

DURING EXPERIENCE

In that span of roughly 14 weeks, the number of mini submissions for this particular module felt exceptionally a lot. However, along the way, I learned to not give up. As said by one of my IA participants, *“Don’t give up in dreams when you think you are able to do it. The key thing is just to stick with it, believe in yourself... and look forward”*. Every assignment I had to submit, every decision I had to make, and all the paths I needed to take, was part of learning, indeed. Sometimes I was thrown to deep ends and torn in catching deadlines but I had to be resilient and stay productive. Self-efficacy was deemed to be especially crucial for goal setting, enactment, and attainment. According to Lippke (2020), self-efficacy theory explains how self-efficacy develops and is altered, as well as how self-efficacy impacts behavioural change, performance accomplishments, and personal well-being.

In regards to our case study assignments, there are moments when I felt like I did not do enough compared to my other group members. My inability to always reply to random discussions on WhatsApp on time either because I was at work and/or not mentally ready to reply messages had always been my key weakness in all the assignments related to our case study. Having friends and group members that were very understanding, was definitely a blessing. I am forever thankful for each and every one of them. The amounts of words-of-motivations we gave to each other during hard times was the driver and the catalyst that kept us moving to finish what we had started. This reminded me of Maslow’s Theory of Human Needs, where things went from the needs for safety (finding group members that I am comfortable working with), love and belonging (friendship and sense of connection), esteem (respect, self-esteem, freedom) and self-actualization (the desire to become and give the best that I can).

One day, someone in the group suggested going to the Tutong market to conduct the study. Myself and one other thought that it was actually a good idea. So early Thursday morning that very same week, we carpooled to the venue and managed to interview five business owners on the spot. With the fact that Tutong Market only opens once a week, we knew it was “now or never”. Even though there were some people who were reluctant to be interviewed, we were eternally grateful for the five individuals who were willing to lend a helping hand and happily contributed to our study. Few weeks before the final submission, we still did not manage to interview a sufficient number of entrepreneurs from the Gadong Night Market. Hence, we decided to go to the Kianggeh Market and interview more business owners. On the day we promised to do the fieldwork, it was only the two of us present while the other one could not be contacted. We still proceeded with the interview nonetheless and managed to interview five more individuals who were very eager to share their motivation as entrepreneurs. Again, it was a tiring Thursday morning for us from interviewing people but we were thankful knowing that class was cancelled that day. At that very moment, I knew the Almighty Listened to our prayers.

Reflecting back on my experience when completing my IA assignment, on the other hand, I realized that I procrastinated a lot. I kept my work to the very last minute which in turn gave me quite suffocating moments. I like to believe that there was a silver lining to it. There were many blessings in disguise. The amount of help I got from family and friends to connect me with women leaders in education out there was tremendous. The last few days before the final IA submission was crucial for me. I knew I needed to finish the task with outcomes that I would be

happy with. With McGregor's Theory Y in mind, I created situations where I respond with initiatives and high performance. This is central to notions of empowerment and self-management (Wardah Hakimah Hj Sumardi, 2020).

I always knew that interviewing people, not to mention leaders will be challenging and need great determinations and endless commitments as they are "busy" people. In my attempt to recruit women leaders for my IA research, I met dead ends, rejections, countless difficulties and embarrassing moments but again, I believe that this is all part of learning that will make me stronger and prepare me for the future. During the last few days before the final IA assignment, I met beautiful and aspiring women leaders in the education sector from different walks of life. Despite their busy schedules, I salute how some women leaders compared to some others are just very open, willing and happily giving some of their time to share their success and challenges as a women leader with me who is just a student, a so-called feminist and an aspiring leader. In addition, I am a believer of the Prophet's saying that "*the best among you are those who bring greatest benefits to others*" (Al-Jarrah, n.d.). Even though I only managed to interview nine women leaders at the end but to me that they were the best among the best, and I learned so much from their experiences.

COMPLETION OF EXPERIENCE

From this module, I learned so many new things such as the existence of a "reflective critique paper" and also a "systematic literature review" especially, which happened to benefit me greatly in other modules, although not in this BM-5102 Organisational Behaviour module in particular. I have also gained so many new experiences especially from interviewing leaders who I have always felt intimidated by all these while. I never knew it was doable until this module inspired me to do so. Strongly humanitarian in outlook, I am an idealist and a committed graduate who is passionate about leadership and equal human rights. I have an eager mind that seeks any tasks and challenges as an opportunity to learn and enhance new skills through practical work with the theoretical knowledge gained in university.

However, one thing I would want to improve if I encountered a similar project in the future would be in regards to my habits of procrastination and keeping work until the very last minute. I have always known that doing last-minute work is a bad idea but reality always hits hard late for me. With the experience gained and lessons learned, it is hoped to successfully help develop me personally, professionally and holistically, also prolonged my exposure to the world. In the case of our group case study assignment, I always wondered would the outcomes be better or vice versa if we went on with a different topic altogether instead of the topic on the motivation of entrepreneurs to become halalpereneurs. I realised that "halal" is actually a sensitive word for some entrepreneurs and my father who works in this area and is facing companies and individuals requesting for halal certifications on a daily basis also agreed to this. Furthermore, I would say that I did not regret choosing this topic as I have gotten the opportunity to attend an online symposium on Halal Science early this October, and listened to the perspectives of the experts in this area.

To conclude, this reflective report is very useful and has helped me better summarize my bittersweet experiences in this module. This difference in writing an academic paper forced me to reflect on the name of this course—how similar to organisations, individual behaviour is also not generic but differs according to time and place.

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